

The Radha Idea at the Crossroads of History, Culture and Politics: *Gitagovinda* and the Boishnob Movement in Bengal

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We shall trace the interconnectedness of historicity and literariness in Jayadeva's *Gitagovinda* using a cultural materialist methodology in this article which will attempt to extend the method of cultural studies to the analysis of this Sanskrit text which was composed more than 800 years ago during the Sena era (we shall very soon turn to the counter-claims which dispute this Bengal aspect of Jayadeva which in our opinion forms the very key to a historical analysis of *Gitagovinda*). *Gitagovinda* forms an important part of Bengal's social and cultural legacy, and this study will also try to develop a composite nationalist method towards reading this literary text. A nationalist methodology shouldn't necessarily be a contradiction in terms (which was discussed at length in the editorial of JBS Vol.1, No.1), as a passionate interest in one's own subject matter is never a hindrance for a disinterested, objective and thoroughly methodical study. In fact, the two are intricately linked. One who is passionate about a subject will have to see to it that the study of the subject does not compromise on scholarly acumen. Further, unless one is genuinely passionate about a subject, the study produced may be mercenary in nature, and may be held ransom to the publish-or-persih motto of the American academia. Therefore, neither one can dismiss those Oriya scholars trying to establish Jayadeva's Oriya lineage (or, Jayadeva-Belonged-to-Orissa, henceforth JBO for our convenience) on the ground of their passionate interest, nor can the Bengali riposte (maintaining that Jayadeva-Belonged-to-Bengal, henceforth JBB for our convenience) be dismissed in a similar way. Our only rider is that such studies have to do academic justice to their subject matter.

Let us begin by examining a few important aspects of *Gitagovinda*. There are certain distinguished features of Jayadeva's long poem which make it an exceptionally great work of art, and place it at the crossroads of Bengal's history, culture and politics. Niharranjan Roy observes:

First, the synthesis between Sanskrit and Apabhramsha and the resultant metamorphosis of the language of his poetry were revolutionary. Secondly, the amalgamation of the supernatural story of gods with the folk story of love was unprecedented and lies at the source of the successive Vaiṣṇava poetry. This synthesis is at the root of the medieval humanism of the Hindu cultural renaissance of the middle ages. Jayadeva was the first to have massively initiated the humanisation of supernatural gods. Many shlokas from *Saduktikarṇāmṛta* also allude to such

an importance of Jayadeva. Thirdly, there is no doubt that *Gitagovinda* is a musical poem, but it has to be admitted that in it there are some signs of a folk dramaturgy (Jatra?), specially the conversation of the consorts of Radha, or the lyrics where Radha and Krishna converse. Actually, in *Gitagovinda*, narrative depiction, conversation-dialogue and music – all the three features are embedded into the poetic form. Such a form was novel and unknown in Sanskrit literature. Fourth, the subject of this poem is religious, but the signification of such poignant folk sensuousness is rare in Sanskrit literature. In fact, such devotional metamorphosis of an original sexual desire is nowhere to be found apart from the *Podaboli* literature of medieval Bengal. Fifth, *Gitagovinda* is at once *Podaboli* (Madhura komalakānta padāvalim) and *Mongol Kabbo* (Shrijayadeva kabheridana kurute mudang mangalam ujjwal geeti), and in this regard, is the fountainhead of the later *Podaboli* literature and *Mongol Kabbo* traditions of Bengal. (628-29)

A very old manuscript of *Gitagovinda*

We propose that *Gitagovinda* can be critically understood with a reference to its space-time co-ordinates, by illuminating its conditions of production, as we explore the interaction between literariness and historicity in this text. Ever since the first English translation of *Gitagovinda* by William Jones appeared in 1792, this work of poet Jayadeva has been translated into different European languages several times. Goethe, after going through the German rendering of *Gitagovinda* highly praised the “extremely varied motives by which an extremely simple subject is made endless” (quoted in Miller x). For the purpose of this article we shall work with English and Bengali critical sources (the latter will be provided in the present researcher's translation), the original text of Jayadeva in Sanskrit as offered in Harekrishna Mukhopadhyay's critically annotated edition (*Kavi Jayadeva O ShriGitagovinda*), and the (UNESCO approved) 1977 English translation of *Gitagovinda* by Barbara Stoler Miller titled *Gitagovinda of Jayadeva: Love Song of the Dark Lord*.

Cultural Materialism is a radical approach to the study of literature associated with the name of Raymond Williams which refutes the conventional base-superstructure dyad of classical Marxism that considers literature (superstructure) as a secondary growth arising out of the primal domains of social and economic forces (base). Instead, the cultural materialist methodology considers literature to be a co-participant in the process of history along with economical and social forces, and detects the interaction between literature and history at multiple levels within the existing discourses of power which are never monolithic but encompass various residual, emergent and oppositional currents (Brannigan 9-13). Simply put, literature, far from being a mirror, a reflection of social realities, often produces history, makes social realities as well as determines our perceptions of them; it shapes religious and economic currents, it often stands at the fountainhead of social, cultural and political movements and gives birth to complex ideological formations within the matrix of history. No doubt, in the process of generating the social, economic, cultural and political forces, literature is also itself constituted by the same forces. Literariness and historicity therefore come to constitute each other in an interactive manner within the process of the production of a text, and the conditions of the production of a literary work leave their complex traces within its texture. So we begin by suggesting that *Gitagovinda* of Jayadeva can be best understood as a product of multiple historical and cultural factors which inform its conditions of genesis (as well as the dimensions of its reception down the ages). And in our opinion the single-most important feature of *Gitagovinda* is the Radha idea. Attempts have been made to trace the antiquity of Radha back to the *Atharva Veda* where both the words Radha and Gopi have been used in connection with the star Vishakha,

as Harekrishna Mukhopadhyay points out in his *Srikrishnoproshongo O Boishnobtottwo* (64). The Brahminical exigency to find a Vedic genealogy for the Radha idea notwithstanding, it has been a scholarly consensus that the Radha idea has very little to do with Vedic monism, that its ancestry cannot really be traced back to Vedas and Mahabharata. Bhaduri conclusively argues that the Boishnob movement in Bengal has no connection with the *Vedas* and *Upanishadas* (17-20). The present researcher would agree.

The centrality assigned to Radha in Bengal's Boishnobism (Gauḍiya Vaiṣṇavism) is an article of faith, a matter of principle. It has been a legend about Chaitanya; when his mind was occupied by Radha, he couldn't even endure any mention of the name of Kṛṣṇa/Krishno as the poet Brindabon Das informs us; once when Chaitanya was chanting 'gopi', 'gopi', a young Vaiṣṇava (clearly not a Boishnob) devotee came to his house and asked him to chant the name of Kṛṣṇa instead. Chaitanya chased the young man away with a stick in his hand (Mondal 52). This unique feature of Boishnobism in Bengal derives its inspiration legacy from the centrality of the Radha-idea in Jayadeva's *Gitagovinda*. This idea of the feminine principle is of ancient provenance in Bengal. It has nothing to do with the *Vedas*. But it can be traced back to the puruṣa-prakṛti dualism of Sankhya, the union of Shiva and Shakti in Tantric cults, the worship of the feminine principle of 'Karuna' (pathos) in Buddhist Mahayana faith, the centrality assigned to the corporal human body in Shohojiya cults (originally Sahajayana, a variant of Buddhism widespread in Bengal, finding their literary embodiment in Caryapada/Chorjapod), the centrality of *porokiya* (adultery) as a philosophical expression of the devotee's union with God, which, as we shall see later couldn't even be understood by Oriya Vaiṣṇavites contemporaneous with Chaitanya. Shashibhushan Dasgupta too notices the strategic position of *Gitagovinda* that encompasses these different cultic practices, mapping their evolutions in Bengal (58). *Gitagovinda* is one of the most crucial watersheds in the trajectory of Bengali cultural-philosophical-religious imagination. It is an integral constituent of the evolution of the Bengali mind across last thousands of years. It is the fountainhead of Bengali Boishnob movement.

Barbara Stoler Miller observes: “Radha is one of the most obscure figures in early Indian literature. Until Jayadeva made her the heroine of his poem, she appeared only in stray verses scattered through various Puranas, anthologies of Prakrit and Sanskrit poetry, works of literary esthetics, grammar, poetry, drama and a few inscriptions” (26). Let us point out that the Radha-idea, which in the process of this investigation we are about to discover at the heart of *Gitagovinda*, can be best understood as a signature of the preponderance of Sankhya philosophy (and its numerous derivatives including certain Buddhist

faiths) in Bengal, and this element firmly places this text within the cultural and philosophical currents of twelfth century Bengal that was already deep with this celebration of the **prokriti** principle now ready to be manifested in the figure of SriRadha. Bankim Chandra in his essay “Sankhya Darshan” observes that the nature of the lived Hindu traditions in Bengal has been derived from the prakṛti-puruṣa (prokriti-purush) dualism of Sankhya, be it the worship of Radha and Krishno or Kali/Durga and Shib (278). As opposed to Bengal, Orissa, a state from where some people have fervently and frantically put forward a claim over the nativity and poetry of Jayadeva in recent times, did not experience the slightest sway (let alone dominance) of the Radha idea prior to the advent of the Chaitanya movement, as Prabhat Mukherjee observes in *The History of Medieval Vaishnavism in Orissa* (43). Needless to say, Chaitanya's movement also operates within an essentially Bengali matrix. Bhaduri in his study on the life and times of Chaitanya repeatedly insists on the Bengal connections of the guru of Chaitanya, Ishwar Puri, and that of the guru of Ishwar Puri, Madhavendra Puri; and in this regard, points out the deeply rooted Boishnob tradition in Bengal which is the “land of *Gitagovinda*” (33), where the poet of Lakṣmaṇa Sena's royal court through *Gitagovinda* sowed the seeds of the divine play of Radha-Krishno (66).

Jayadeva and Padmavati in a conventional depiction of the anecdote where Jayadeva discovered that Kṛṣṇa himself came and wrote the phrase *dehi padapallavamudāram*

The Radha idea also stems from the Sahaja Yana (The Easy Path) Buddhism of Bengal which celebrated the centrality of erotic love as a method of worship, and equated the human body with the universe (the concept of *bhande/brohmande*). Harekrishna Mukhopadhyay, noted *Gitagovinda* scholar, observes that

the Sahajiya/Shohijiya (the follower of the Sahaja) sects of Buddhism were dominant in Bengal prior to the age of Jayadeva, and they were later loosely brought into the fold of Gauḍiya Vaiṣṇavism – the same proposition is forwarded at length by Dinesh Chandra Sen (324-329) – while these Shohojiyas considered Jayadeva as their *adi-guru* or first mentor. Mukhopadhyay refers to Haraprasad Shastri in this regard; Shastri opined that Jayadeva's *Gitagovinda* is deeply committed to the Shohojiya philosophy (which observed that the union of man and woman is the ultimate aim of the universe) in its lyrical celebration of the conjugal love of Radha and Krishna (*Kavi Jayadeva* 25, 26). Mukhopadhyay explains at length the intricate relationship between Jayadeva's poetry and the Bengali Shohojiya traditions:

Prior to the advent of Jayadeva, the practices of Buddhist Shohojiya sects became especially popular in the Rarh region. One branch of this Shohojiya community under the influence of Nityananda accepted Boishnobism but did not give up their own cult practice completely. These very people are known as Boishnob Shohojiya. ... this community honours Jayadeva as their first Guru and one of the nine connoisseurs (*nobo-roshik*). ... According to Haraprasad Shastri, Jayadeva was particularly indebted to the Shohojiyas. The pleasure of sexual union which was the only desirable state for the Shohojiyas was harboured in the union of Radha and Krishna by Jayadeva's expression... (*Kavi Jayadeva* 25)

The celebration of the dominance of prokriti over purush (signified in our times by a forceful Kali standing atop a passive Shib, or immortalised in Jayadeva's text by the legendary *dehi padapallavamudāram* phrase) was essentially a mass cultural practice since time immemorial, which was later appropriated by the dominant Vedic hierarchies.

Krishno holding the feet of Radha, in a Boishnob artist's imagination

The worship of the shakti/yoni dates back to very ancient times; the purush-prokriti dualism of Sankhya philosophy is a highly evolved form of the ancient fertility cults which not just lie at the root of Tantric and Shohojiya Buddhism practised in Bengal, but also inform the core of the later Shakto and Boishnob faiths in this part of India. Here in Jayadeva we can detect a primeval residue beneath the veneer of the dominant, as beneath the Brahminical wrapping we can observe the vestiges of an ancient matriarchal form of culture. This text in its celebration of classical *Śṛngar rasa* covertly celebrates the folk Shohojiya cults which find their fullest embodiment in the Radha idea. Indeed, no Krishno worship is possible in Bengal without the evocation of Radha, as there is no Krishno temple in Bengal without Radha as the co-deity, and reading *Gitagovinda* helps us in understanding this lived tradition. Though there is no denying the fact that *Gitagovina* was composed from a royally privileged position of authorship which firmly placed this text within the *Puranic* Brahminical traditions which were being promoted during the Sena rule, we can nevertheless find some vibrant rudiments of the deeply rooted non-Vedic culture of Bengal in the celebration of SriRadha in Jayadeva's masterpiece. It is interesting to note that the poet himself is aware of the rich collage of diverse materials, social conditions and historical paraphernalia which have gone into the making of his poetry. One couplet, where the poet speaks of his native village Kenduvilva (shown by Prasanta Kumar Dasgupta in his critically acclaimed studies to be the Joydeb-Kenduli of Birbhum district of West Bengal, as we shall see later in this article) which compares the birth of the poet with the emergence of the moon from the mythical churning of the sea (*samudra manthan/shomudro monthon*) is particularly curious, because this couplet seems to exhibit an ancient awareness of the richly complex, **overdetermined** (to borrow the Althusserian concept) birth of poetry. Further, *Gitagovinda* is not just a royally patronised text standing in isolation on the top of an ivory tower. The author displays a crucial awareness of being part of a group, a milieu, a cultural current, a dominant idiom of an erotic stylistics (characterising the cultural output of the Sena court in general). It has indeed been proven beyond doubt by a particular couplet of *Gitagovinda* that Jayadeva adorned the royal court (of Lakṣmaṇa Sena/Lokkhon Sen) along with four contemporary poets: Umapatidhara, Govardhana, Sharana and Dhoyi. The shloka does not mention the name of Lokkhon Sen, true, but anyone reading that shloka without a bias will agree that it is implicit there: that together these five poets constituted a closely-knit group of contemporaries. They themselves were the proverbial 'five jewels' of the royal court of Lokkhon Sen, because, for Jayadeva, there can be no other significance of taking the names of other contemporary poets unless they shared some palpable bond, a common ground where they could be

compared to each other. Jayadeva is not taking the names of great predecessors as if in observance of a poetic custom; poets did not customarily take the names of other contemporaries in a spirit of comparison unless they were familiar with each other (logically speaking, knowing a number of contemporaries was out of question anyway in the absence of printing press; if indeed the JBO claim was true and Jayadeva was writing in far-off Orissa in isolation from these four Bengali writers, he couldn't have possibly known them). Further, two shlokas from *Saduktikarṇāmṛta* (a compilation by Śreedharadasa, a collection from the poems of the renowned writers of the Sena age, including the Sena kings themselves) authored by Jayadeva praise the king of Gauḍa and Vanga, as we shall see in details later.

Lee Siegel points out that Jayadeva observed the contemporary royal conventions of poetic composition throughout *Gitagovinda* (204); further, the presence of the epithet “Radhamadhavayorjayanti” in the opening stanza of *Gitagovinda* is a case in point, as the same phrase occurs in a verse authored by Lakṣmaṇa Sena and in another verse authored by Keshava Sena (both of them appear in *Saduktikarṇāmṛta*) (Prasanta Dasgupta: 1982: 18). That this was a conventional catchword of the court poetry of the Sena kings is evident, and Jayadeva's use of this epithet firmly places him within that milieu.

Gitagovinda bears witness to a richly synthetic Vaiṣṇava (Boishnob) tradition in making; Lee Siegel notes: “Lakshmanasena (sic) is described in the court records by the title *Parama-Vaishnava*, but although he was officially a devotee of Vishnu, worship of, devotion to, other gods seems to have been encouraged. It was a time of syncretic trends – Jayadeva's inclusion of the Buddha in the list of *avatars* (I.13) is indicative of the attitude” (211). Dinesh Chandra Sen too considers Jayadeva's evocation of Buddha is a characteristic feature of the amalgamation that goes on to produce Bengali identity (9, 330). In a similar vein, the synthesis of the Radha idea with the conventional decorum of Sena court poetry is intricately constituted in *Gitagovinda*. Further, Jayadeva successfully attempts an amalgamation of Sanskrit and Prakrit in his poem, the result of which is a fluent, easy, idiomatic, melodious and free-flowing diction which closely corresponds to the popular speech (Sen 296). It has been further noted: “The rhythm of *Gitagovinda* does not follow the trajectory of Sanskrit; instead it shares an intimate relationship with Prakrit rhythms”; and this feature of Jayadeva's poem has led some researchers to argue that and Jayadeva's *Gitagovinda* renders the existing Prakrit/Proto-Bengali folksongs of Radha and Krishna into Sanskrit (Sen 496). In fact, as history attests, there used to be a genre of erotic love songs of Radha Krishna called *Krishnodhamali* in the proto-Bengali language which might have influenced

Jayadeva; the same genre most certainly influenced the later poet Chandidas in writing *Shrikrishnokirton*. Kalidas Roy observes the deep legacy which Jayadeva's poetry leaves behind; he notes the imprint which its style, form and content leave on the later Bengali poetry, particularly the *ShriKrishnokirton* of Chandidas and the medieval Boishnob *Podabolis* (79-80). As the present researcher would like to point out, Jayadeva's *Gitagovinda* can be understood even today without the help of any Sanskrit lexicon by anyone who has a good knowledge of chaste Bengali.

If we trace the lineage of the Radha idea in ancient India – Miller also traces the first mention of the word “Radha” back to *Atharva Veda* (27) – the text of *Gitagovinda* reveals itself as a palimpsest to us. The juxtaposition of orthodox male tradition of *Puranas* (the text of *Gitagovinda* begins with an evocation of the Daśavatara of Viṣṇu) and the heterodox folk tradition of Radha worship can be located at the source of the trajectory of the Bengali school of Boishnobism. Interestingly, it has been argued that the evocation of Daśavatara places *Gitagovinda* within the context of Nimbarka school of philosophy, which also incidentally puts a very high value on Radha as the supreme principle of the Krishna incarnation (Prasanta Dasgupta: 1982: 47). What is extremely significant here is the evolving dimension of the sacred in an erotic poem like *Gitagovinda* as it turns into a religious text of pan-Indian significance over the following centuries, as the poem comes to be intimately associated with devotional and ritualistic practices and performances of lived traditions of Vaiṣṇavism in India. However, closely investigated, the text reveals itself to be an inseparable part of Bengali faith, culture and tradition. *Gitagovinda* is a text that skilfully conjoins the ancient traditions of celebration of the feminine principle within an orthodox Vaiṣṇavist framework and infuses the substance of prokriti worship into the structure of Vaiṣṇavism in order to produce the supreme manifestation of the Radha idea, which heralds the gestation of Gauḍiya Vaiṣṇavism (Gouriyo Boishnobism). *Gitagovinda* is the watershed which would distinguish Boishnobism from Vaiṣṇavism, which would signal the birth of the Bengali Joydeb from a Sanskrit Jayadeva, which would be the midwife of Bengali identity. Jayadeva's poem operates within a multi-layered framework, that, when subjected to cultural materialist analysis, yields some interesting glimpses of the interrelatedness of historicity and literariness.

Let us rehearse our arguments so far. Since time immemorial, Bengal had been under the sway of the great tradition of Sankhya, and when a born again Vaiṣṇava movement reached out to the Sankhya philosophy of male-female dualism evolved and derived from ancient fertility cults, which had at its

centre the worship of the feminine as the origin of power (*shokti*), it gave birth to the Radha idea. The motif of the Radha-Krishno duo (just like the Shib-Kali duo) represents an ancient lineage, albeit in a Brahminised format. Further, it draws profusely from a Shohojiya system of worship native to Bengal and of primeval provenance. In this way, the formation of Boishnob cults of Bengal (Gauḍiya Vaiṣṇavism) exhibits a typical trajectory of Hinduism, and is a classic example of the synthetic, syncretic indigenous tradition that is known by the name of Hinduism. It encompasses both Vedic Brahminism as well as resistances against that. Bengal has never been a part of the Vedic culture, characterised by monism and its emphasis on yajna. It is imperative for us to understand the complex nature of Sena culture where a Brahminical edifice reveals an indigenous infrastructure. This turn to Kṛṣṇa would encompass an appropriation of a godhead from north India at the hands of Shohijiya cult, and the prokriti principle dominant in Bengal's own Buddhism which is metamorphosed as the Radha idea. Throughout our history, Bengal has witnessed the emergence of myriad cultural practices all of which celebrate the feminine principle, most popularly known as *shokti*. Dinesh Sen writes:

Shiva himself destroyed the yajna of Dakṣa. The whole of Bengal was against Kṛṣṇa and the yajna-performing Brahmins at one point of time. Then the flag of Bholanath (Shiva) was fluttering across this land. The Brahminism harboured around Kṛṣṇa was not popular here then. Afterwards, Shiva abdicated his empire in favour of the yajna-prohibiting, equality-professing, treasurehouse of compassion Buddha. After many ages when this country accepted Kṛṣṇa, he had to step on the soil of this land renouncing his *Shankha-Chakra-Gadā*. Bengalis pledged loyalty to him after placing a flute in his hands. (41)

What Sen does not write here is that Krishno could enter Bengal only after submitting to the *shokti* of Radha. Though it has sometimes been argued that Brahminism is a syncretic, accommodative discourse which tends to welcome other faith systems, but this argument lacks substance. Left on its own, Brahminism has always produced most suffocating, exclusionary and oppressive forms of casteism. The syncretic tradition of Boishnobism in Bengal has flourished, **in spite of** the Brahminical dominance, as a result of the preponderance of non-Vedic cultural systems (also, heavily influenced by the Dravidian, Austric and Mongoloid strata in Bengal).¹

It is argued at times that Indians do not have a sense of history. Some saffron historians have been cautious not to fall victims to the 'trap' set by western academia, by trying to historically investigate the

Ramayana narrative (surely it is a convenient facade to hide behind myth and claim immunity for all problematics and questionnaires of history). A noted saffron intellectual argues that Indians do not have a sense of history (Rajiv Malhotra in his book *Being Different*), and he suggests that in a positive manner. On the contrary the present researcher would suggest that Indians do have a sense of history. The problem of the history of the Hindus precisely started when censorship began to be imposed on Buddhism and Buddhist history. When a timeless aura had to be invented around a newly instated (not reinstated or restored; it was a Sanatan Dharma newly fashioned) Brahminical system after ousting Buddhism, a deliberate attempt was made to blur genealogies and past accounts. Buddhism and Jainism are known for their minute attention to temporal frames, and there have been many Indic traditions which have been renowned for keeping records. But our history was in jeopardy and was manipulated, because, not content with one of the most ancient philosophical traditions of the world (*R̥gveda*), some Brahmins greedily wanted to eliminate all competitions to their creed. As an aside, this aspect of Vedic Brahminism might also have informed the manipulation of Jayadeva's history carried out by the JBO lobby (refer to Endnote 1). Jayadeva's *Gitagovinda* is a text that was born in those circumstances when Bengal's Buddhist-Shohojjiya history was a problematic category and could only be voiced after being thoroughly clad in Brahminical diction, and its troublesome history ever since is a testimony to that Brahminism-induced fissures and faultlines in our past. Still, a valid history of Jayadeva can be excavated without any substance abuse, and we can settle it once and for all that this text's as well as its author's origins lie in Bengal. Those who support the view that Jayadeva belonged to Orissa have repeatedly emphasised on the Bengali scholar Sukumar Sen's doubts about Joydeb-Kenduli. Well, this attempt to establish the JBO claim is academically dishonest, because Sukumar Sen never proposed an Oriya identity for Jayadeva. On the contrary, he is a firm adherent of Jayadeva's traditional image as the court poet of Lakṣmaṇa Sena. All he disputed was the existence of Joydeb-Kenduli. He suggested that Joydeb-Kenduli is a later day development (to draw a parallel, like the present-day Vr̥ndavana is a medieval invention) and it is not the original Kenduli village of Jayadeva which Sen suspects to have been lost. More about Sukumar Sen later, but referring to Sen's argument about Kenduli in support of the JBO claim over Jayadeva is a serious compromise with academic standards, but then such compromises overwhelmingly characterise the JBO claim as we shall see. Let us examine the evidences in favour of the traditional claim that Jayadeva-Belonged-to-Bengal. Noted historian Niharranjan Roy specifically draws our attention to the depiction of the famed Bengal monsoon that is repeatedly hailed in the literature produced in ancient Bengal.

There are a number of poems from the collection *Saduktikarnāmrta* which celebrate monsoon, and Roy refers to a Pāla (Pal) inscription in this regard, commenting: “And, during the heavy-solemn and dense rain, the way the rapt sky is greeted as “meghairmedurambaram” by the Bengali poet Jayadeva and the image in which its dark-blue grandeur is manifested, that is singularly familiar to the Bengalis and that can only be applicable about Bengal, we think” (105). *Sekaśubhodaya* is another ancient text (which albeit exists in a corrupted version scripted in fifteenth century, but its original text was composed by Halāyudha, a contemporary of Jayadeva in the Sena court) from Bengal which mentions the story of Jayadeva and his wife Padmavati in an essentially Bengali setting (Niharranjan Roy 254). Prasanta Dasgupta also emphasises the role of *Sekaśubhodaya* in understanding the times of Jayadeva (*Jayadeva Contemporaries* x). It is interesting to note that Niharranjan Roy does not show an unqualified admiration for Jayadeva as he disapprovingly note the ironical gap between the critical political condition prevailing at the time of the production of *Gitagovinda* and its erotic appeal. When India was being taken over by an aggressive force of Islam, the Sena Kingdom was busy celebrating sexual love in its numerous poetic works, the spirit of which finds its heightened expression in Jayadeva's poem. Similar criticism of Jayadeva has earlier been voiced by Bankim too, as Harekrishna Mukhopadhyay notes (*Kavi Jaydeva* 1). However, we cannot fail to observe that such a critique indirectly establishes the JBB claim over Jayadeva. The overall cultural atmosphere of the Sena court was charged with motifs of sexual desire, and Jayadeva's poem is deeply anchored in that morass. Niharranjan Roy comments:

Jayadeva himself is saying, that there was no parallel of poet Govardhana in composing flawless erotic poetry. *Arya Saptashati* bears witness to that. And Jayadeva's *Gitagovinda* too is an erotic poem in a palpable sense; the main feature of this work is the imagination of an exhilarating poetry of sexual desire. Saint poet Nabhaji Das of sixteenth century in his *Bhakta Mala* calls this work a treatise of desire and a treasury of erotic *rasa*. Materially speaking, the best poems of this age are intoxicated and sweetened with sexual desire and a luxury of wealth. (425)

However, here Roy does not recognise one important aspect of *Gitagovinda*, and his training as a historian within positivist values might not have helped either (both Bankim and Niharranjan decry the sexuality in Jayadeva from a positivist perspective, as the present researcher would like to suggest). The cultural politics of a literary text can have a far-reaching significance beyond its immediate utility

and expediency. To put it in a very blunt manner, this seems to be Niharranjan's (and Bankim's) contention: instead of this poem of erotic love, Jayadeva should have written a valiant poem of military rigour which could have formed the backbone of Sena resistance against Turkish aggression, motivating the Sena armies to rise against the forces of invasion. However, the cultural import of this text as the fountainhead of Gouriyo Boishnobism perhaps presents more striking and more sustained an act of resistance against the aggression of Islam than what could possibly have been the case of some knee-jerk poetic reaction against an immediate threat of invasion. For centuries the music and lyric of *Gitagovinda* offered people a cultural framework, a performative utterance of one's faith, a sublimation of a core human desire into an expression of the highest spiritual communion, an epic symbolism of the purush-prokriti dualism in the godheads of Radha and Krishna. It might not have given any help to the Sena armies, but it has given invaluable help to the formation of the counter-culture of Boishnob faith in Bengal. If Jayadeva did not write *Gitagovinda*, we couldn't have the Chaitanya movement. Harekrishna Mukhopadhyay rightly observes that without the literary impetus given by Jayadeva, the Boishnob movement couldn't have formed their powerful community (*Kavi Jaydeva* 17). True, the cultural appropriation of a text by future times is a matter which is not very often determined by the immediate nuances, merits and structures of that text itself, and is rather decided by the future exigencies. The hugely popular text of *Gitagovinda* was used by Bengali Boishnob movements in a manner so that it became a religious text, as Jayadeva attained a posthumous status as a devotee (*bhokto*) extraordinaire, and the mellifluous songs of *Gitagovinda* went on to become signature anthems of Boishnob faith, providing a model of inspiration for later Boishnob poets and composers. Perhaps the popularity of this text is also the key to its infrastructure: it was popular because it struck a chord very close to the heart of the Bengali people as Bengal has been the home of Sankhya and Shohijiya philosophies. The dualism of Sankhya has been worshipped here since time immemorial in its different manifestations, and that dyad finds its popular embodiment in the figures of Radha Krishna in Jayadeva's poem which in the same breath celebrates the Shohojiya concept of erotic love. Niharranjan Roy considers the emergence of Radha idea to be a Bengali phenomenon:

That in some period not long before Jayadeva (twelfth century) the philosophy of Radha and the imagination of the Radha figure were born in this very Bengal cannot be probably doubted. Materially speaking, the Radha of Vaiṣṇavism is a metamorphosed and rechristened Vaiṣṇava form of Shakti of Shaktoism. Kṛṣṇa or Viṣṇu (like Shiva) is the ultimate *puruṣa* in Vaiṣṇavism

and the *prakṛti* or *shakti* of this *puruṣa* is Radha. This earth or *prakṛti* is the *shakti* or *vaiṣṇavi* of Viṣṇu, this thinking did spread in the sixth and seventh centuries. Perhaps Radha is an evolved form of this thinking. (499)

When the text of Jayadeva is thus excavated, what we unearth there is nothing short of that primeval ocean out of which the texture, matrix and composition of the modern day Bengali identity would emerge. For Niharranjan Roy the origin of the Chaitanya Vaiṣṇavism lies in the *daśāvatāra* shloka of *Gītagovinda*, who points out that in Śrīdhara-dāsa's *Saduktikarṇāmṛta* a similar evocation of the *daśāvatāra* philosophy. Niharranjan further opines that the majority of these shlokas were composed and sung in the court of Lakṣmaṇa Sena (a devout worshipper of Kṛṣṇa, who fashioned himself as paramabhāgavata) (548).

Further, Jayadeva represents the making of the composite nature of Bengali identity, and was not a Boishnob in a monolithic sense. Niharranjan Roy informs us: “Jayadeva did not just hail Radha-Madhava; he was not singularly Vaiṣṇava either, he was a worshipper of the five divinities” – worship of the five, namely Shiva, Shakti, Viṣṇu, Ganesh and Surya characterised the Purnaic consciousness – and that Jayadeva was a familial (as opposed to ascetic) Brahmin of the *smārta* tradition; his shloka about Mahadeva is quoted in *Saduktikarṇāmṛta* (551). Jayadeva was not simply a devoutly religious person as the supporters of JBO like to believe; he was very much a man of his times: a part of the royal court, enjoying royal patronage, sharing the court ethos and lifestyle, observing the literary conventions of his circle. There is a shloka written by Jayadeva collected in *Saduktikarṇāmṛta* which eloquently sings the praise of Lakṣmaṇa Sena, and Niharranjan Roy quotes that four-line shloka in full, musing that Jayadeva might have made his appearance in the royal court of Lokkhon Sen with this shloka (623). That the erotic love story of Radha and Krishno was hugely popular in Bengal prior to Jayadeva (in eleventh century AD) is evident in one Sanskrit shloka from *Subhāṣitaratnaḷoṣa* as observed by Ramakanta Chakraborty, which speaks of devotees melodiously singing in early mornings of winter the lyrics which depicted the secret love of Radha and Krishno (13). King Lakṣmaṇa Sena was himself a writer, apart from being a devotee of Radha and Krishno. Indeed, it has been observed by Sukumar Sen that the first shloka of *Gītagovinda* was written by Lakṣmaṇa Sena himself, as the latter penned a number of shlokas on Radha and Krishno which end with the phrase “Radhamadhavayorjayanti” which is also the case of the first shloka of Jayadeva's poem (quoted in Hazra 19). On this very phrase, noted linguist and philologist Suniti Chatterjee says:

The refrain-like agreement in the first part of the fourth line in all the three verses ("Radhamadhavayorjayanti...") is to be noted. These three verses probably record quite a pleasant episode in the verse-compilation by emulation in the court-circle, in which the ruler, his son and the most esteemed poet of the day took part, with the other members of the circle participating with approbation, one of whom, the anthologist Sridharadasa, recording all the three poems of the royal poets for posterity. (quoted in Prasanta Dasgupta 33)

This scholarly agreement between Chatterjee and Sukumar Sen establishes a critical consensus about Jayadeva whose writing style and use of phrase(s) constitute a continuum with the royal Sena court.

While Niharranjan Roy unhesitatingly declares that the Kenduli village on the banks of the river Ajoy is the birthplace of Jayadeva based on a number of evidences (629), a strange controversy in this regard is started by Sukumar Sen, who is under any circumstances not a supporter of the JBO case. Almost all the supporters of JBO have quoted Sukumar Sen out of context in their haste to prove that Jayadeva was Oriya. Sukumar Sen indeed said that Kenduli village of Jayadeva is lost and the present festival of Kenduli is a later day invention. But Sukumar Sen never denied the essentially Bengali origin of Jayadeva, or that Jayadeva was the court poet of Lakṣmaṇa Sena. The fact is that Sukumar Sen indeed contends that there is no village called Kenduli, and what is called the Kenduli fair is so named simply by convention (Hazra 19). Prasanta Dasgupta calls this proposition of Sen "manifestly absurd" (*Jayadeva Contemporaries* 21). Kenduli is a village in Birbhum, as we can also see in the study of Lina Chaki who has attended the fair herself. Harekrishna Mukhopadhyay, the Boishnob scholar extraordinaire who lived in Birbhum himself attests at length in his *Kavi Jayadeva O ShriGitagovinda* that the village called Joydeb-Kenduli where the annual fair is held very much exists. We may never know why Sukumar Sen made that outrageous claim. But that he did not visit Kenduli himself, that is for sure; may be he was being driven by the familiar critical impulse to sound as different as possible, so as to draw attention to him. The Kenduli village of Birbhum exists in all land maps and records, therefore any attempt to debate the existence of this village is a wasteful exercise. Prasanta Dasgupta's collection of British colonial maps and land records of Kenduli in his book (the one in English) is a neat academic job (22), and a fitting response to this mindless controversy started by Sukumar Sen and should settle this contention once and for all.

The legend of Jayadeva indeed lives in the annual fair of Kenduli in the Birbhum district of West Bengal. There is a detailed study of the Joydeb-Kenduli fair (as it is celebrated) in Lina Chaki's book (29-53).

Chaki, while agreeing with Sukumar Sen's contention that the present fair dates back to relatively recent times (Chaki dates it back to 1694 CE following Sen), suggests that the Snanjatra (the holy dip) performed annually on the banks of Ajoy river on the day of Mokor Shonkranti (Makara Sankranti) – which is really what the Kenduli fair is all about – might have been contemporaneous with or even older than the days of Jayadeva (35-36). In any case, if a historian can imagine that all indigenous rituals (collectively given the name Hindu by our invaders) could continue unhindered and uninterrupted after the Turko-Afghan invasion of Bengal, then that is not an objective, substantial appraisal based on empirical evidence; that is rather a piece of airy idealism. We cannot expect the Kenduli fair to have continued uninterrupted throughout the middle ages. Prasanta Dasgupta usefully informs us in this regard:

In the year 1614 of Saka era, i.e. 1692 A.D., a temple of Radha-Madhava was built by the Maharani of ... Burdwan. It is said that the original image was brought from Shyamarpur Gad, a place near Kenduli. Those, who say that the history of the existing temple near the place of mela began from 1694 A.D., may note that had there been no tradition of Jayadeva connected with this place, the Maharani of Burdwan would never have built a temple there in honour of poet Jayadeva. (*Jayadeva Contemporaries* 22)

One interesting piece of information provided by Prasanta Dasgupta (23), (and repeated by Chaki) is that the Joydeb-Kenduli fair since its inception in renewed avatar in 1692/1694 has been organised by the saints and monks belonging to the Nimbarka order. It has been observed that the Nimbarka order celebrates Jayadeva as one of its chief saints, and that the centrality of Radha idea has been instrumental in the teachings of Nimbarka, the founder after whose name this order is christened. Prabhat Mukherjee too observes the pioneering role of Nimbarka (a Telugu ascetic who resided in Vṛndāvana during thirteenth century) in propagating the Radha idea: “The conception of Radha has been given a prominent place in in the teachings of Nimbarka” (70). This corroboration of Joydeb-Kenduli of Birbhum by the Nimbarka order (which is an all India sect pre-dating the birth of Gouriyo Boishnobism; Nimbarka order is almost devoid of Bengali Boishnobs) further consolidates the Bengali tradition about Jayadeva's birth place.

Harekrishna Mukhopadhyay draws our attention to the age-old Bengali Boishnob tradition which states that Sanatan Goswami (of the legendary Rup-Sanatan duo) saw the following shloka sculpted on a Nabadwip ruin of a royal gateway which said that the court of Lakṣmaṇa Sena had these five jewels:

Govardhana, Sharana, Jayadeva, Umapati and Kaviraja (Dhoyi) (*Kavi Jayadeva* 19). This tradition attributed to the court of Lakṣmaṇa Sena readily resonates with the shloka in *Gitagovinda* which speaks of the unique strengths of these four poets (Govardhana, Sharana, Umapati, Dhoyi) and then compares Jayadeva favourably with them. Further, two shlokas of Jayadeva from *Saduktikarṇāmṛta* celebrate the valour of the king Lakṣmaṇa Sena (one addressing the king as Gauḍendra and Vangapriya, the other addressing him as Rajendra) and Mukhopadhyay considers them to be evidence for Jayadeva being Lakṣmaṇa's court poet (*Kavi Jayadeva* 24). Further, Mukhopadhyay makes a cursory observation that a veteran researcher named Buehler saw the mention of Lakṣmaṇa Sena in a manuscript of *Gitagovinda* in Kashmir (*Kavi Jayadeva* 25). Mukhopadhyay does not further mention anything, but noted German Indologist Johann Georg Buehler's 1877 work *Detailed Report on a Tour in Search of Sanskrit Manuscripts in Kashmir, Rajputana and Central India*, published from Bombay is a major compendium of nineteenth century Indology which, unfortunately, in spite of repeated searches of the present writer couldn't be accessed on any archives in the internet. However, this work by Buehler must be traced and studied minutely as an essential algorithm to decode Jayadeva, since a number of Bengal manuscripts were dispersed after the Turk-Afghan invasion of western Bengal. As we know, a number of manuscripts were brought to Nepal and Tibet, and from there an odd manuscript making its way to Kashmir does not seem quite improbable.

While speaking of the algorithms of a text, we need to investigate its time-space co-ordinates. An ahistorical idealism has reigned in Bengal eversince our model of literary enquiry was adopted from Tagore. Instead of history, transcendence was chosen as a norm. The relative had to make way to the absolute. local was replaced with universal, context was discarded in favour of timeless truths, time-space co-ordinates were given up in search of genius, nationalism was cancelled in favour of an autonomous self-fashioning; and as a result, Bengalis actually thought that the literariness of Jayadeva's work was independent of the conditions of its production. Prasanta Kumar Dasgupta records that the supervisor of his doctoral thesis on Jayadeva, renowned Professor Srikumar Bandyopadhyay “did not encourage me to include non-literary discussions like the birth-place controversy of Jayadeva” (*Jayadeva Contemporaries* ix). This reveals a certain callousness of the twentieth century Bengali mind towards Bengal's history, and this actually disarms our people in front of aggressions like the JBO poaching of Jayadeva. Thankfully, not only Prasanta Dasgupta continued to work on the history of Jayadeva, his post-doctoral work on the birthplace controversy of Jayadeva was very highly acclaimed in the All India

Conference held in 1972 in Ujjain and was awarded the best paper's prize, as Dasgupta humbly informs in *Jayadeva and Some of His Contemporaries* (ix).

Harekrishna Mukhopadhyay observes in his preface to Prasanta Dasgupta's 1974 book (in Bengali, derived from the original doctoral thesis of Dasgupta) *Gitagovinda O Jayadevagoshthi*: “Finally let me mention about a lamentable conspiracy. Of late, for some years some Oriyas motivated by a vested interest have become busy in establishing poet Jayadeva as an inhabitant of Orissa. Orissa government too is assisting in this disgusting act” (ঈ). Mukhopadhyay in the same breath commends the painstaking research undertaken by Dasgupta in resolving this controversy, and the fact that Dasgupta's work on Jayadeva has been accepted and appreciated by the community of historians and Indologists. However, *Gitagovinda O Jayadevagoshthi* does not have that chapter on Jayadeva birth controversy which Mukhopadhyay so earnestly wanted to be a part of this study, chiefly because of the said objection of Srikumar Badyopadhyay. Prasanta Dasgupta informs us:

Whether poet Jayadeva was Bengali or Oriya – I was very much interested to include a long discussion on this topic in this book. Dr Bandyopadhyay told that this matter is irrelevant in the evaluation of the poetry of Jayadeva. We shall not concede if the Oriya scholars call Jayadeva Oriya. We cannot make them agree to our proposition of Jayadeva as a Bengali. ... Actually only after the arguments of both sides are exhausted the enthusiasm for debate will decrease. (৬)

This lofty imagining of neutrality and this assumption of not belonging to any sides in the spirit of a liberal, universal-humanism (*bishshomanobota*, as we call universal humanism in Bengali) would come to constitute a distinct feature of the Tagorean ethos which has been so very dominant in Bengal ever since the fall of nationalistic feeling, and which has been behind the steady depletion of the Bengali people during the later part of twentieth century. That such celebrations of a universal humanism has been an imperial strategy, enacted out within the colonial and postcolonial scenarios by the bhadralok-compradors of Bengal has been a key proposition enabling the basic analysis of the Bengali predicament since the present researcher founded *Journal of Bengali Studies*. Interestingly, it has been observed by a critic that “throughout history, empires, such as the Roman and Ottoman, have sought to unify their peoples as a political alternative to nations” and thus, to “recognize oneself as a part of humanity” is a central ideological impetus of imperialism (Grosby 4). But apart from the nationalist critique of it, universal humanism is also vulnerable to be reduced to the status of shibboleth in any contemporary

literary analysis and can certainly appear outdated in any cultural enquiry. We believe that an informed understanding of Jayadeva's poetry must address the history of its production and subsequent reception, as any such understanding must acknowledge the poet's time and space.

The first claim for an Oriya identity of Jayadeva was made by Madhav Pattanayak in his *Vaiṣṇava Leelamṛta* as Mrityunjoy Mondal notes (21). Pattanayak, a disciple of Gadadhar Pandit, was a contemporary witness of the Chaitanya movement. The same text of Pattanayak also puts forward a claim for an Oriya lineage of Chaitanya. Mrityunjoy Mondal has observed that most scholars do not accept an Oriya claim on Chaitanya; quoting noted Chaitanya scholars Bimanbihari Majumdar and Sukhomoy Mukhopadhyay, Mondal himself has attempted to show that the class of Brahmins to which Chaitanya belonged did not exist in Orissa. Likewise, the claim that Jayadeva was Oriya, in Mondal's opinion constitutes a fabrication that is motivated by 'regionalism' (21). In the opinion of the present researcher, this attempt by Pattanayak is analogous to the attempt of (some) Indian Christians to establish that Christ came to India, or that Saint Thomas came to India and died in present day Chennai. Such claims are politically motivated and not are primarily concerned about historical accuracy. Such claims are anxious to place a newfound land of a proselytising faith in a position superior or equal to the land of origin that faith. Such fabrication is an emotional act born out of an anxiety, a psychoanalytical appropriation of one's new identity, and a rebellion against the original alienation of one's faith. The JBO claim builds a narrative where past is rewritten, and is made suitable for the present, and the dominance of Bengali Boishnob culture in Orissa is made to appear as indigenous as possible.

Let us revisit our proposition that the Radha idea lies at the core of *Gitagovinda*. The most crucial aspect of Bengal's Boishnob movement is the centrality of the Radha idea in it. And every inch of *Gitagovinda* is a typically Bengali work in that it is infused with this Radha idea – as Mukherjee comments, “Radha-idea is perfected, perhaps for the first time, in *Gitagovinda* of Jayadeva” (70) – which was alien to Orissa prior to the advent of Chaitanya's movement. Prabhat Mukherjee in his *The History of Medieval Vaisnavism in Orissa* observes: “The reference to *Gita-Govinda* in the inscription of Kapilendra is interesting. The book received an early ovation in Orissa though Radha-idea, the quintessence of its theme, was not popular in the pre-Chaitanya age” (43). Ramakanta Chakraborty in his study observes that the existing school of indigenous Vaiṣṇava philosophy in Orissa called 'Panchashakha' (which existed prior to and contemporaneously with Chaitanya movement) did not

attach any importance to Radha. According to one of the chief proponents of this Panchashakha *Vaiṣṇavas* (namely, the Oriya poet Balarama Dasa, who composed Ramayana in Oriya language), Chakraborty notes, “the relationship between Radha and Krishna was that between a sister and a brother; the idol of Subhadra between the idols of Jagannath and Balaram in the temple of Puri signifies this relationship” (47). Chakraborty hints at a major ideological rift between the Oriya and Bengali devotees caused by such incompatibilities which ultimately led to an exodus of the Bengalis from Puri to Vṛndāvana which personally traumatised Chaitanya as his attempts at reconciliation failed (47).

Mrityunjoy Mondal informs that Raya Ramananda who was considered to be a pillar of the Goudiyo Boishnob movement and was dear to the Bengali stalwarts of Boishnobism (including Chaitanya) was treated in a hostile manner by the Oriya Vaiṣṇavites who ultimately exiled him out of Orissa: “According to Oriya researcher Bishnupada Panda, the Shohojiya devotion was against the religious tradition of Orissa. ... His being sent to the Godavari region was in a sense an exile sentence for the *bhakti* movement centred around love” (70). This Shohojiya Boishnobism had its origin not in Orissa but in Bengal. Seemingly, the line of Ramananda continued to show the same attachment to the Bengali Boishnob tradition. Prasanta Dasgupta tells us:

Manohara Dasa, said to be the great-grandson of Vaninatha Pattanayaka, brother of Ray Ramananda the great friend, philosopher and devotee of Srichaitanya, first came to Burdwan, following his elder brother Nityananda from Jajpur where his forefathers resided. He went to this Kenduvilva village by accepting Gourhari Vaul as his Guru in the 17th century A.D. *Dinamani-candrodaya* by Manoharadasa a 17th century work narrates the fact. This shows the tradition of Bengal Kenduli was popular even amongst the 17th century Orissan people. (*Jayadeva Contemporaries* 23)

At times a scholar may wonder why at all this JBO versus JBB controversy took place, when we had people like Ramananda and Manohara. Bengal and Orissa have been historically culturally and above all geographically close and share a lot of things in common. The fact that Jayadeva visited Orissa was not to be disputed any historians. But the fact that the JBO camp indulged in this futile exercise to detach Jayadeva from every palpable context which informs his poetry is really unfortunate. What is most interesting is that the JBO proponents have forgotten that a sizeable part of Orissa (including Puri) indeed came under the occupation of Lakṣmaṇa Sena. A very interesting information in this regard is shared by Purnendu Prasad Bhattacharya:

In 1174 AD Lakṣmaṇa Sena erects a SamayaJayastambha (Victory Pillar) in the holy pilgrimage place of Puri after defeating the Ganga King of Puri Ananga Bhima Deva, and arranged for *Gitagovinda* to be regularly sung in the newly refurbished Jagannath temple (upon the third vastu level). ... Jayadeva went on to live on the banks of a river near Cuttack for some time and by Lakṣmaṇa Sena's order, the river was rechristened Ajaya and that village on the river was rechristened Kenduli. (7)

That Lakṣmaṇa Sena invaded Kalinga and occupied large tracts of it is an established fact of history. The authoritative *An Advanced History of India* by R.C. Mazumdar *et al* while recording Jayadeva's connection with the court of Lakṣmaṇa Sena tells us that Lakṣmaṇa Sena “served his apprenticeship in the work of government as viceroy or military governor in charge of some district in Kalinga. On coming to the throne, he distinguished himself as a conqueror and a patron of learning. He claims to have pushed his conquests as far as Kalinga” (180). Dinesh Sen observes that the Madhainagar copper inscription records the conquest of Kalinga by Lakṣmaṇa Sena (490). The same copper plate proudly proclaims Lakṣmaṇa Sena's amorous liaisons with the women of Kalinga, and this erotic allusion later comes to form the nucleus of Dhoyi's *Pavanadūtam* which is modelled on Kalidasa's *Meghadūtam* (Sen 506). *Pavanadūtam* speaks of a Gandharva damsel named Kuvalayavati suffering from her pangs of love for a youthful Lakṣmaṇa Sena after he has left Kalinga (Niharranjan Roy 624). R.C. Mazumdar in his *Ancient India* notes that Lakṣmaṇa Sena, who conquered a number of provinces and whose victory march extended to Kamrupa in east, Benaras and Allahabad in the west and Kalinga in the south indeed planted a victory pillar in Puri (320-321), a fact that is never mentioned by any of the JBO scholars. While Lakṣmaṇa Sena's Madhainagar grant tells us of the conquest of Kalinga (among other conquests), the Madanapara grant of his son Viśvarūpa Sena informs us about the victory pillar which was raised in Puri by Lakṣmaṇa Sena (Pal: Vol.1: 92, 94). In this regard, we think that Bhattacharya's work needs to be taken seriously, as it throws a very interesting light on the birthplace controversy. Bhattacharya evidently relies on contemporary Sena declarations, inscriptions, documents and the *kulaji* texts (works of medieval genealogies). Lakṣmaṇa Sena's occupation of Kalinga which is a historically documented fact might be analysed as a factor towards decoding the popularity of *Gitagovinda* in Orissa and as a possible clue to unravel the birthplace controversy. This view reconciles the JBO and JBB claims, and thus definitely merits a careful appreciation.

Prasanta Kumar Dasgupta while extensively discussing about the controversy created around Jayadeva in his 1982 study called it the “birth-place controversy,” and indeed at that point of time the controversy was probably limited to the birthplace of Jayadeva. Now it has engulfed Jayadeva's identity as the court poet of Lakṣmaṇa Sena. The campaign against Jayadeva's Bengali/Gauḍiya identity has been most successful on the internet. Wikipedia and online Encyclopedia Britannica both record the version forwarded by the JBO camps. A chief secretary of Orissa has written an article on the website of Orissa government which betrays very poor research and flawed arguments (not to speak of outright mistakes) where he attempts to prove that Jayadeva was native to Orissa and he never went to the Sena court.² The same person has also been instrumental behind the claim that Gautam Buddha was born in Orissa.³ Looking at this article on Jayadeva by one of the main campaigners for the JBO cause, one will invariably get an impression that the fact of Lakṣmaṇa Sena's 'cowardly' flight from Nadia (Nodia) is forwarded as a singular evidence that Jayadeva could not have belonged to this king's court.

A historian must defend his people: this might as well be a slogan of nationalist historiography, and would undoubtedly sound scandalous to liberal ears. But Niharranjan Roy seems to take the side of his people while discussing Bakhtiyar Khilji's conquest of Nadia (it was **not** the conquest of Bengal). Niharranjan Roy painstakingly establishes the facts, removing the veils of myth, and as a result what emerges is a history of the Bengali people which Bankim must have jubilantly approved, because it absolves the Bengali people of the charge of cowardice. Bakhtiyar Khilji was disguised as a horse trader while occupying the Sena outpost (not the capital) of Nabadwip, while the Sena court itself was teeming with fifth columnists and traitors, some of them being the rank and file of the Sena administration (Niharranjan Roy 409-415).

We voiced a rider about nationalist fervour in academic studies in the beginning of this article, and as we are approaching the end of our study, our only objection should be that the JBO scholars have not been passionate enough about Jayadeva to notice the infantile nature of their anti-Bengali polemic, the tremendous rubbish which they have heaped on the history of Jayadeva of late, while their works indeed prove that they are less driven by a genuine passion to know about Jayadeva and *Gitagovinda* than by a burning jealousy of Bengal and Bengalis. It is somewhat amusing to note the institutional, *sarkari* sponsorship which the champions of the JBO cause have enjoyed in Orissa. Funnily, **not** a single argument (all of them are flawed anyway, as Prasanta Dasgupta has painstakingly shown in his studies) provided by the JBO lobby actually establishes an Oriya identity for Jayadeva. Prasanta Dasgupta almost

throws his hands in air in exasperation after a lengthy refutation of all the JBO arguments, precisely because all that the JBO scholars have claimed is that Jayadeva did not belong to Bengal, while not giving a single argument in favour of Jayadeva's Oriya identity, as if the poet would automatically belong to Orissa without any historical evidence, just by slandering the well-established tradition of Jayadeva's Bengali roots. Such a disreputable, dastardly act has only been able to go on unchallenged because of the liberal indifference as befits the Bengali *bishshomanobota*, amnesia and assumptions of neutrality even when they necessitate turning a blind eye to the aggression carried out against one's core cultural, social, philosophical and literary capitals and legacies.

Orissa's tableau at the Republic Day Parade in 2011, in New Delhi. Note how Jayadeva, seemingly in the act of composing *Gitagovinda*, is foregrounded to the Jagannath temple

It has been falsely claimed by one Dr Mahapatra that the JBO theory is supported by the *Bhaktamala* of Nabhajidas, a hagiographic work composed in seventeenth century during the reign of Shahjahan, as Prasanta Dasgupta cites (*Jayadeva Contemporaries* 19). As a result of the pan India *Bhakti* movement, there was a proliferation of hagiographies during the seventeenth century and many of them took inspiration from Nabhaji, as Prasanta Dasgupta tells us; further, he quotes the relevant passages from Nabhaji and shows that there is absolutely no reference to any Orissa connection of Jayadeva, whereas a commentary ('tippani') on Nabhaji's *Bhaktamala* composed by Vaiṣṇavadasa (significantly, a Nimbarkite) speaks directly of Jayadeva belonging to Birbhum (*Jayadeva Contemporaries* 20). The oldest known commentary on *Gitagovinda* composed (sometime between 1438 and 1459) by Maharana Kumbha of

Mewar titled *Rasikapriya* speaks of Jayadeva in connection with king Lakṣmaṇa Sena, as Prasanta Dasgupta informs us in the same study (20-21). Dinseh Sen informs us that a shortly after the composition of *Gitagovinda* a commentary on it was produced by Krishna Datta of Mithila (500), which also mentions Jayadeva's role as a court poet of Lakṣmaṇa Sena (492). We must agree that the case for Jayadeva's Bengali identity and his relation with the royal Sena court has an ancient provenance. The JBO claim, on the other hand, is upstart. As Prasanta Dasgupta notes, there is absolutely **no** mention of Jayadeva's Oriya identity throughout the eighteenth and nineteenth century annals of Indology and Oriental research: "Early scholars and orientologists have recorded the claim of Birbhum district and of no other places. Had the claim of Orissa been popular in the late nineteenth century even, it would have been mentioned by W. W. Hunter in his famous book *Orissa (or the Vicissitudes of an Indian Province under native and British rule)* published in 1872"; interestingly, as if adding insult to injury, not only Hunter is mentionless about Jayadeva's so-called Oriya identity, he in fact categorically speaks of "[t]he Beerbhum poet Jayadeva" while commenting on the Jagannath Temple (13). The silence about any JBO claim in Hunter's annal of Orissa clearly indicates that the village of Kenduli Sasana in Puri district touted to be the birthplace of Jayadeva has benefited from a latter day fabrication, and has basked in a belated glory heaped on it in twentieth century. If Kenduli Sasana of Puri district was known as the birthplace of Jayadeva at the time when Hunter was writing his work, it would have surely been reflected in the content.

The fallacies in JBO arguments are quite interesting. It has been questioned by the JBO scholars that if Kenduli in Bengal was the birthplace of Jayadeva, then why did Chaitanya never visit that place? A bemused Prasanta Dasgupta points out that such JBO arguments completely ignore the fact that Chaitanya never visited the village of Kenduli Sasana of Puri either (*Jayadeva Contemporaries* 21). Some of these arguments are outright fun: like the regular performance of *Gitagovinda* in the Puri temple is presented as a proof that Jayadeva was an Oriya, or that the erotic sculptures of the Orissan temple architecture are forwarded as evidence which would establish that Jayadeva was an Oriya (Prasanta Dasgupta: 1982: 23). Anybody wanting to get a comprehensive account of JBO claim over Jayadeva needs to look no further than Diananath Pathy *et al* and be cognisant of some of their cretin arguments which reek of fraudulence, suppression of history, manipulation of data and outright misinformation. We may taste this: Umapatidhar cannot be associated with the court of Lakṣmaṇa Sena because he was associated with the court of Lakṣmaṇa Sena's grandfather Vijaya Sena (Pathy 21), whereas Niharranjan

Roy's authoritative work clearly establishes the fact that Umapatidhar was alive even after Bakhtiyar Khilji's raid of Nabadwip (624-625). Or for that matter, let us take the JBO doubt about the shlokas of Jayadeva from *Saduktikarṇāmṛta* eulogising the Sena king: here, this is the contention; being a saint poet who was completely devoted to Krishna (note: **not Radha-krishna**; JBO scholars betray their gross ignorance of the basic Radha idea, which dominates *Gitagovinda*, in every piece of propaganda they have churned out in order to establish their claim over Jayadeva) Jayadeva couldn't have written them, and they must be coming from some other Jayadeva (Pathy xvii). First, Bengali historians are aware of other Bengali poets named Jayadeva who composed in Sanskrit, as Dinesh Sen attests (369), and there is no question of confusing them with Jayadeva who belonged to the court of Lakṣmaṇa Sena. Only the crudest, basest form of ignorance about the contemporary court writings during the period of Lakṣmaṇa Sena can facilitate such utterances. Jayadeva was not a saint, he was an artist deeply imbued within the dominant cultural practices of the Sena court. The overtly erotic nature of *Gitagovinda* can only be missed if it is turned into a fossilised piece of esoteric chants, which is the case of the plight of *Gitagovinda* at the hands of the JBO claimants. And this is why we regularly face from the JBO camps such pious proclamations of Jayadeva's saintliness and his devotion to Jagannath/Krishna, which brutally uproot Jayadeva from his historical milieu and commit an unprecedented violence on *Gitagovinda*.

This JBO attempt to make a pulp out of history can be considered to be a cretin variant of the Imaginary stage as proposed by noted psychoanalyst Jacques Lacan. Imaginary is the pre-symbolic stage of human subjectivity; simply put, it is the stage prior to a human child's entry into language. The world of a baby around itself (parents, table, chair, bed, own urine and faeces - it doesn't differentiate betwixt itself and these) appears to it as an extension of its own body, its own image. If this child is cretin, then it can forever stay in this Imaginary stage. The JBO possessiveness over Jayadeva operates as a cretin Imaginary. Without understanding Jayadeva's language at all (the style, diction, ideology, context), the odd claimant considers Jayadeva to be a part of its own image.

Those few medieval works seemingly corroborating the JBO claim over Jayadeva might have taken their cue in this regard from the work of Madhav Pattanayak composed during the time of Chaitanya, as we have already discussed. Needless to say, they are weak matches for the contemporary works surviving from the twelfth century Sena court. Prasanta Dasgupta's scrupulous research (in Bengali and in English) on all the contemporary poets of Jayadeva from the Sena court remains authoritative to this day and firmly places Jayadeva within the literary-cultural-philosophical movements of the Sena age, which will

continue to exert conscious and unconscious influence on the Bengali mind for centuries. From the postmodern, parodist use of *Gitagovinda* in the popular music of Chandrabindoo to the ample mentions of *Gitagovinda* in the popular fictions of Sharadindu, Jayadeva's poem has become a part of the collective idiom of Bengali cultural expressions. And its position within the Boishnob movement of Bengal exudes an original significance. Bengal has been fertile in producing poets and poetry across centuries, and therefore we may not feel desperately fanatic about Jayadeva as if he is our sole treasure, to go to any length to procure that treasure by hook or by crook. We may not feel greedy towards the proverbial rain of *Gitagovinda* the way a barren, drought-ridden, rocky and sandy terrain might feel, but that does not mean Jayadeva is dispensable, and that barren terrain may have him, and we can turn a blind eye to the JBO poaching of Jayadeva in a liberal fashion, with an outdated neutrality and suicidal cowardice. History attests: *Gitagovinda* belongs to Bengal, and today for a nascent analysis of the Bengali identity, reclaiming what has always been rightfully ours is critically important. The historicity and literariness of Jayadeva's text constitute an integral part of the political, cultural and social foundation of the Bengali people.

A traditional depiction of a Gauriyo Boishnob procession led by Nitai and Gour

Endnotes

A Note on Transliteration: We have tried to conform to the standard (internationally recognised) spelling of *Gitagovinda* and Jayadeva throughout this article. However, while speaking of Jayadeva within an essentially Bengali context, be it in the title of Bengali studies on the poet, or the fair of Kenduli, Birbhum, we have preferred the spellings Joydeb and *Gitgobindo*, preferring the Kolkata standard of Bengali language. Bengalis pronounce the Sena kings as the Shen kings, but the spelling Sen is so familiar, we had to use it instead of Shen while speaking of the Sen court and Lokkhon Sen in a Bengali context. Further, the present writer has tried to provide correct diacritical marks to all Sanskrit terms, but would like to apologise for whatever lacunae that exist even after his best attempts.

1. This may interest us that the JBO lobby voicing its claim over Jayadeva overwhelmingly consists of Oriya Brahmins, and have been accused of Brahminical prejudice by fellow Oriyas who have also alleged that the village touted to be the birth-place of Jayadeva is arbitrarily and falsely chosen. One can see the details here: <<http://orissamatters.com/2005/05/17/birthplace-of-jayadev/>>. Accessed on 4 February 2014.

2. This is a jointly written article where one of the co-authors is an additional chief secretary of Government of Orissa. <<http://orissa.gov.in/e-magazine/Orissareview/dec-2006/engpdf/dec.pdf>>, The same person has written another article under sole authorship peddling the claim that Jayadeva did not belong to Bengal <<http://orissa.gov.in/e-magazine/Orissareview/2011/may/engpdf/18-20.pdf>>. Both accessed on 4 February 2014. Note that the Orissa government solidly backs the JBO camp (as opposed to the Bengal government whose attitude always exhibits a liberal nirvana. This article repeatedly says that Lakṣmaṇa Sena escaped from Bengal after Bakhtiyar Khilji's raid, which is ridiculous. All historians agree that Lakṣmaṇa Sena (by this time more than eighty years old) went to eastern Bengal where the Sena dynasty continued to rule for at least another century, successfully repelling repeated Muslim assaults, Lakṣmaṇa Sena's both sons Viṣvarūpa Sena and Keśava Sena proudly taking the titles of Gauḍeśwara and “Garga-Yavanānvaya-Pralaya-Kālarudra” which categorically imply that they repeatedly defeated the Muslims (Pal: I: 98). Minhajuddin in his *Tabaqat-i-Nasiri* notes that Lakṣmaṇa Sena went to a place called Jagannath, and Dinesh Sen convincingly proves that this was a village named Jagannath (in the Jessore-Khulna region) in east Bengal (543). We may have some legitimate critiques of the Sena rule, but we fail to understand how a charge of cowardice may be brought against Lakṣmaṇa

Sena, or how a distortion of Sena history will be helpful in studying the poetry, life and times of Jayadeva.

3. With the same signature authorship, this time the pioneer of JBO camp makes an attempt to poach on Gautama Buddha, no doubt emboldened by the cakewalk which they have enjoyed in their campaign to occupy Jayadeva. <<http://orissa.gov.in/e-magazine/Journal/journalvol11/pdf/orhj-3.pdf>>. Accessed on 4 February 2014. It may not be irrelevant to note here that an attempt was made to alter the wikipedia article on Buddha by this lobby, which created a furore amongst the Wikipedians, and that misinformation (that Buddha was born in Orissa) was immediately removed. The success in manipulating the Jayadeva Wiki-article no doubt encouraged the JBO lobby. We may also note that there have been similar campaigns of misinformation in Wikipedia regarding some other cultural treasures of Bengal, for example the Wiki-article on Roshogolla says that it was invented in Orissa. See <<http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Rasgulla>>, <<http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Jayadeva>>. Both accessed on 4 February 2014.

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